

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

WYRED Consortium Manifesto

English Version

WP4_D4.1

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1 Introduction

A central aim of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) is to give children and young people a voice, particularly in relation to research into issues that concern them, and how its results are discussed and presented.

A manifesto written by the consortium exists to declare our intentions.

2 Manifesto

The WYRED consortium believes that children and young people's voices are not sufficiently heard in society, or taken into account in decisions. This is especially true in research contexts, where the young rarely define the agenda.

The WYRED consortium understands children and young people as a heterogeneous group that must be addressed in all its immense diversity. WYRED offers a space for individual engagement, where children and young people are active creators and explorers, rather than passive consumers.

The WYRED consortium perceives that decisions taken in relation to "digital" issues increasingly impact the whole of society. These decisions should therefore take into account all of society, and this requires participatory inclusive approaches that ensure decision-making will be relevant and appropriate for all those affected.

To address these issues, WYRED will provide an opportunity to children and young people to voice their concerns. First through a process of social dialogue where their views are surfaced, and then through the design of participatory research projects where they explore their concerns and enrich their perspectives with the evidence they find. These perspectives are then shared with policy makers and the public.

The WYRED consortium is committed to the facilitation of the engagement of children and young people, and to ensuring safe participation by reducing vulnerability and promoting online resilience and self-organisation.

The central aim of the WYRED project is to provide children and young people with a way of shaping the society they live in, and the world they inherit.

2.1 Values and principles

The WYRED consortium has a strong commitment to the values of non-discrimination, (regardless of age, gender and sexual orientation, social and cultural background, political or religious belief), freedom of expression and speech, respect for human rights, dignity and care. The WYRED activities will be shaped in accordance with these values:

Diversity - we value diversity as integral part of this digital society we inhabit. We believe in the power of self-expression, performance of identities and the chance to reinvent oneself but, at the same time, respecting others and their freedom in an atmosphere of equality.

Openness - we will establish and nurture a climate of dialogue and openness to others' opinions and perspectives, so that WYRED is a safe space in which all feel welcome and can feel free to be themselves, we will respect the privacy of others, and their dignity and values, in the understanding that these may be different to ours.

Participation and engagement - we will provide equal opportunities to youth of all ages, backgrounds and walks of life without being judgemental but assertive and supportive. We will spread the word and encourage others to engage themselves in the process with us and express their opinions but also speak up for those that still can't.

Good faith – in all the interactions in WYRED, we will be fair, open, and honest, regardless of the outcome of the interaction and make our best efforts to ensure these values are upheld, to ensure the health of this digital community we live in.

Support – we will support and facilitate the activity of children and young people, while respecting their autonomy and their capacity to take decisions and organise their activity, and we will encourage them in the exercise of their freedom:

- To be heard.
- To be safe and supported.
- To be appropriately informed.
- To control the use of their own data, and to be forgotten if they wish.

- To be free from discrimination, harassment and other aggressions.
- To shape their future through active participation.
- To develop and extend this list.

2.2 What we aim to achieve

The children and young people who participate in WYRED will know that their voices matter and that they are the ones defining the WYRED research agenda.

The WYRED platform will function as a safe space in which children and young people can express and share their concerns, and explore the perspectives and interests most relevant to them.

The WYRED network of children and young people will provide opportunities for sustained international and local interaction, across boundaries, celebrating diversity.

The WYRED research cycle will generate insights and perspectives capable of illuminating and informing policy and the wider society. The results will support and strengthen the voices of the young, making it easier for them to communicate with policy and other decision makers.

The WYRED project will raise and develop awareness of the evolving rights and needs of children and young people in the digital society, and provide evidence that will help policy and other decision makers to adjust social, legal, and policy mechanisms to these emerging needs.

3 References

- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). The WYRED Project: A Technological Platform for a Generative Research and Dialogue about Youth Perspectives and Interests in Digital Society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.